

Study of the Negative & the Positive Impact of Coronavirus Pandemic on Different Types of Industry, Businesses & the Society

Shubham Parsoya¹ and Dr. Asif Perwej²

^{1,2}School of Management Studies, Sangam University, Bhilwara, Rajasthan, India.

¹shubhamparsoya369@gmail.com, ²dr.asifperwej@gmail.com

Abstract: In the background of unforeseen occurrence scenario of COVID-19 nationwide pandemic, this paper has created an endeavour to study the impact of coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) on differing kinds of companies and industries in numerous ways. Once the emergence of Corona pandemic in India introduced, the matter of public health condition has become core issue of the people in India and it's been on the forefront in conjunction with alternative and related serious issues of migrant labour, loss of employment, economic and industrial instability etc., and on the other side with the massive population size and its ever growing rate over the last 3 decades, the general public health scenario has been deteriorated significantly, and the occurrence of COVID-19 since 2019 has changed the entire world's functioning accordingly. Internationally the Pandemic of COVID-19 has affected all sections of the economy and nobody will specifically predict when the pandemic is going to be over and everything are going to be like our past days. With the beginning of the unfold of COVID-19, business and various other industries, such as; region trade, transport industry, food industry, agriculture industry, housing industry, education industry, cinema industry, energy industry, producing industry, music industry, mining trade, were straightaway clean up, and the outside travelling and domestic travel activities were also withheld for the unknown length on such moment. The impact of Covid-19 on all such industries was very big. Globally all business and industry are witnessing serious threat with the spreading of COVID-19. All the countries have the first preference of the protection of the people, interference of unfold and health care of the infected folks. However, there are some types of industries that are becoming some extreme number of advantages from such COVID-19 pandemic conditions in some direct or indirect ways. Such industries are; Education (EdTech) industries, E-retail industries, Banking, financial services and insurance industries (BFSI). Medical sector, Information technology and knowledge Technology Enabled Services, Etc.

Keywords: Pandemic, COVID-19, Industries, Businesses, Impact, Problems, World, Economy.

Article History

Received: 12/02/2021; Accepted: 06/03/2021

Corresponding author: Shubham Parsoya, Email id: shubhamparsoya369@gmail.com

Introduction

After observing this state of affairs of various nations and up to level of recent development-based activities, the report follows through bound niches where the government of different countries and several world leaders engaged themselves in taking some concrete actions and policies for safeguarding the whole world from this internationally expanded disaster. They made discussions regarding solutions and suggestions, particularly throughout the sensitive time to heal the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. This pandemic actually created different types of problems for the common man too. As it shaken up all the policies up to great level, it's a terrible tragedy with insurmountable loss.

The COVID-19 pandemic impact on the higher education system in almost both the ways; negative ways and positive ways. Negative impact are the examination of the scholars don't seem to be conducted in the upcoming days too, whereas all the institutions, teaching centres where new admission processes take places are now hampered or discontinuous for a long and uncertain period of time, whereas on the other hand, the positive impact is that the digital technology especially for delivering educational teachings is continue to implement by almost all the educational units where they applying on-line teaching and learning techniques. As we all know that education plays a crucial and demanding role globally in developing a talented man. Because of which mostly as per our traditional education systems, the utilization of textbooks and notebook has been the standard technique of instruction and it's restricted within the schoolroom, however within the twenty first century as ever-changing the character of science & technology teaching, the academic spaces gets the advantages of digital learning and teaching, attributable to that data of academics goes on the far side of the schoolroom and its actually unfolding worldwide.

Coronavirus (COVID-19) has been declared as pandemic and its impact on the whole planet is however be totally assessed. Social group peoples living in their regions are unlikely have any thought of going outside of their places because of the fear consisting in their minds. This paper delineates the Impact of COVID-19 on social group people also, we all analysed and noticed that the COVID-19 destroys economies, jobs, homes, making food resources very much scare, etc.

The thoughts of coronavirus have led to a large shift in people's behaviour, like bulk-buying or self-isolating, which directly and indirectly have impacts over the whole economy.

The magnitude of the economic impact can rely upon the period and severity of the health crisis, which somehow created the period of the internment for almost we all, and therefore the ways during which such things unfold, will easily hamper the activities of the whole world, the state of the Indian economy also faced the potential impact of the shock on varied segments of the economy, analyse the policies that are proclaimed up to now by the central government and therefore the banking concern of India to ameliorate and manage the economic shock and advance a collection of policy recommendations for specific sectors. As COVID-19 becomes a world pandemic and, it's a lot more necessary than each and every one must analyse the situations in its real ways. But somehow the COVID-19 pandemic also introduced several types of new marketplaces which were previously untouched, that will ever-changing the behaviour patterns of the whole customer segments too, and will produce new opportunities for marketers, Additionally, to its impact on people and communities.

Methodology

As per the stipulations of the expressed study, the analysis is employed for the study of the descriptive sorting. For this reason, the accessible secondary data-based information was all at once and broadly used for the analysis purpose. A lot of distinguished level of exactitude in considering the accessible data and its in-depth investigation associated with the topic was thought-about. For the Analysis & the Study of the Negative & Positive Impacts of Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19) on Different Types of Industry, Businesses, Activities & the Society, this research paper relies on the investigation which is connected and depending upon the information received and sourced from numerous libraries books, reliable diaries, journals, different types of magazines, pertinent books, topic-pertinent articles, reports, media, Etc.

Highlights of the Negative and the Positive Impact of Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19) on the Businesses and Industries

There is no argument that the whole world's economic and social spheres, similarly as internationally gets into various types of changes after COVID-19. Some faced severe challenges and a few sectors are drastically razed. The differences present in socio-economic structure and cultures of different countries faced unparallel level of negatives and positives because of the coronavirus pandemic. As we all know that, considerable level of changes taken places in the

service sector, the manufacturing sector, the economic, and the agricultural sectors. In relation to these sectors, government had taken considerable level of steps to make the things again in its control, that includes policies formulations for industrial sector, the agricultural sectors and the service sector, primarily.

However, our industrial sector is going to be severely broken because of COVID-19. Especially, the textile business is going to be heavily broken because of coronavirus pandemic, since the pandemic has severely affected big countries like the USA and European countries, this may cause lesser or almost no demands for readymade industries, therefore resulting in the closure of the many attire industries within the country as well as outside the world. The factories wouldn't be ready to overcome the scenario like this, as in the case of COVID-19 the export volumes of the agricultural and fisheries sectors decreased up to almost zero, or somewhere it reached to the negative levels, also. Especially the economic sector and social sectors on all countries get severely affected because of COVID-19 pandemic.

What the negative impacts?

The pandemic state of affairs has unfolded as a worldwide illness that is making worry, stress, stigma, minimizing social networks, etc. Health and medical systems, particularly medical specialty systems, have taken their utmost efforts to deal with the situations and to safeguard the people from the negative impacts of the pandemic. However, the aid system itself is affected because of numerous complexities presents in its functionality. Thus, there are several deaths reported worldwide although including the medical specialty staffs. The high rate of deaths because of numerous sicknesses or complications of diseases occurring amongst the patients, particularly the people who are aged. It is not possible that the medical team can handle all such tasks and challenges completely own their own basis, a proper set of supporting employees, social employees, and health directors, police forces and other support systems are the need of such situations at domestic, as well as world levels.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) is the primary entity followed by UN that are accountable throughout the whole world to encounter world pandemic related affairs. For handling such pandemic situations almost every country considerably focused toward the arrangement and controlling mechanisms without focusing all the other issues which were traditionally much in considerations. Some countries like Spain, the USA and China, Italy, and

many different European countries face a far higher disintegration towards the society, because of the severe pandemic situations where the whole things may go out of the control. Thus, the social structure wants a whole reorganization and integration to survive. The short time dismantlement of the relationships and the social communications with relatives, neighbours, numerous communities gave rise to some sort of mental discomfort and frustrations. These conditions might result in social conflicts and force within the family. For re-establishing the required level of connections among the societies along with following the “social distancing”, several leaders of various countries conducted various types of programs and events.

The economic conditions of various families get disturbed and a number of lower sections of the social categories are facing intolerable economic hardships because of lack of daily or monthly earnings. Although there are market accessibility and supply chain network to present in this pandemic situation, but because of the various limitation of social groups such as, lack of financial resources, massive population size, etc. the whole distribution system got seriously affected. In terms of educational sector, disruptions of faculties, universities, and education segments, the basic need of the students got unfulfilled, as the students are not allowed to go to their educational institutions because of the severe situations generated because of coronavirus pandemic. Due to which, students faced some irreversible gaps in their education.

People had faced numerous forms of stress, social issues, and depression conditions because of the uncertainty created in their daily lives, all because of the coronavirus pandemic. Potential social conflicts or conflicts of interests within the subsystems of the society was taking places. Some establishments and organizations might not possess enough capacities to seek out remedial solutions to fill the gaps and problems. The decline in belief systems and practices in all religions and other might take places, as people started not to believe in the religious powers, in god and different divine and invisible components, that’s all because of the mood-swings taking places in the psycho mental behaviour pattern of the people.

There is also some temporal decline in distributional mechanisms of goods and services, due to which goods and services are not completely and transparently transferred from one place to the other and such type of conditions will give some extra advantages to the black marketers to do black marketing. After looking into the pandemic situations where the availability of goods and services get completely disturbed, such situation gave chances to various shopkeepers to do black marketing of daily useable items and they also started to charge almost ten times of the

original prices of such goods and services. And on the other hand, sometimes public may depend upon rumours and alternative informal channels of data about the situations that were actually fake news that seems like real one and do generate a chaotic condition on the dissemination of such data, these rumours may create completely discomforts in the social and economic groups. This could cause some negative attitudes amongst alternative social categories by making a conflict of interest.

The pandemic situations also result in monetary crises like a decline in financial values, share market values and businesses, changes in networking, and also the buying power of the individuals hampered due to the coronavirus pandemic. All countries have to take various action to keep up a stable economy. Especially the developing countries and poor countries intended to get additional loans and grants for its economy to survive. Thus, there'll be additional economic and political dependency in these countries, that will ultimately result in financial burden on the economies of the developing countries. Due to such financial aid, countries directly or indirectly fulfil their daily needs for a short period of time within the territories, but somehow their financial conditions for the upcoming future also get hampered.

The pandemic scenario can directly influence the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlined to be achieved by 2030, as some of the countries might not be able to allot monetary resources to fulfil the country-specific targets, because of the loss taking places due to coronavirus pandemic. Internal fragmentation could occur in world countries, significantly within the USA and that they could plan to regain the power through varied economic and political methods.

What the positive impacts?

People learned various things regarding social distancing, conditions, and procedures. Especially, the importance of family system and conjointly the community, as most of the times they spend together with their family members in the coronavirus pandemic lockdown situations. Also, they adapt themselves according the situations with a hope to regain everything in much better ways. As a result of social integration, families, and communities engage at an awfully high level of social cohesion or social conscience to face a troublesome state of affairs, sharing and caring for others, significantly their family members.

Most of the world's industries and manufacturing units stops working for few months of times, because of which there is a considerably level of decrease in the carbon levels and harmful

gases created because of these industrial operations. The reductions in the release of such harmful gases for such a short period of times will ultimately help the whole planet to recover itself from the prevailing harmful impacts of air pollution. With the result of which the overall air quality index of the world air quality improved at certain levels and the overall environmental degradation reduced up to certain levels. From environmental point of view the Reduction in the use of plastic and synthetic resin usages at the domestic level, International level get subsequently reduced and it will directly help in environmental protection. As a whole, it contributed to world environmental protection efforts. Especially, it should quickly cut back greenhouse gases, thanks to the minimum use of vehicles and industries all over the world. Perhaps, there could also be some climate changes within the surroundings. Reduction within the environmental pollution within the world, regional and national contexts. Mainly, air pollution and sound pollution are going to be reduced. There are some studies conducted, and that they reveal that the pollution level is reduced drastically altogether.

A type of similar connection can be easily visible in the social, environmental and socio-cultural levels, where the overall behavior pattern of the people also gets improved up to certain level. Domestic production may increase because of family or house level agricultural practices as well as different small-scale handicraft productions in society. This may help in scaling back the market demand to some of its previous extent and it's going conjointly to cause positive effects amongst international trades. Intergenerational social integrity can strengthen and be consolidated by youths. There'll be an increased demand for several new and innovative fields of businesses at national, regional, and world levels, because of the social and physical distancing. The Decline in defense expenditure at national and world levels maximizes the funds availabilities for the necessity or needs based goods and services on a brief basis. Thus, war-based worries may be reduced at sure levels in almost all the regions of the whole world. New philosophical constructions in several vital subject disciplines, like drugs, economics, government, sociology, psychology, robotic sciences, spiritual and humanistic sciences encouraged by almost every country in the lockdown period of coronavirus pandemic.

Hence, analysis and development activities expanded in almost every country. Developments in social science and social engineering skills to deliver economical services throughout the networks and management of patients and the general public are enhanced with great pace, and adapted to follow optimum use of resources, economizing resources, and property approaches to

satisfy their basic requirements first. These trends might reorganize the networks at national and International levels. For a very long period of time, there is no such big terrorism related activities come into happening because of the stoppage on the fund raising and fund transferring by these terrorism organization, and that ultimately results in the decrease in the overall cases of any terrorism related attacks and incidents.

Steps Taken by Government of India to handle the COVID-19 Pandemic Situations

The Government of India declared several policies to handle the impacts of COVID-19 pandemic, from food security and further funds for care and for the states to sector-related incentives and tax payment date extensions. On March, 2020 variety of economic relief measures for the poor were declared totalling over ₹170,000 crores (US\$24 billion), subsequent dealing with the banking concern of India additionally declared variety of measures that may build on the market on the market, ₹374,000 crore (US\$52 billion) to the country's national economy.

The different phases of India lockdown mechanisms up to the "first unlock" on one June had varied degrees of the gap of the economy. On April, the Reserve Bank Governor declared a lot of measures to counter the economic impact of the pandemic by ₹50,000 crore (US\$7.0 billion) special finance to NABARD, SIDBI, and NHB. For Indian corporations throughout the pandemic, the govt modified India's foreign direct investment policy. The Department of Military Affairs placed on hold all capital acquisitions for the start of the fiscal year. The Chief of Defence employees has declared that country ought to minimize pricey defence imports and provides an opportunity to domestic production to encourage the sense of self-reliant India.

The Prime Minister declared an overall economic package value 20 lakh crore (US\$280 billion), Rs. 374,000 crores of India's gross domestic product, with stress on country as a self-depended and self-reliant nation, throughout subsequent 5 days, the government minister declared the diverse portions of the economic package subsequently and later on 2 days the policies regarding the variety of proposals within the economic package was introduced and several free food grains package schemes were introduces for the betterment of the society.

New Technologically-Driven Developments in the Functioning of Whole World

COVID-19 has incontestable the importance of digital readiness, that permits business and people's life to continue with the advancement of digital technologies of different types for availing the workings of different fields. Such as, education, banking, e-marketing, online buying and selling activities, etc. as a common task throughout pandemics. Building the required

infrastructure to support a digitized world and keep updating within the latest technology are going to be essential for any business or country to stay competitive in such situations of COVID-19 worldwide. COVID-19 pandemic work like an catalyst for digital transformation in some direct ways, unexpectedly, And can greatly accelerate many major trends that were already well afoot before the pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic can have an enduring impact not solely on our economy, but also on the tendency to of the daily life-based activities of the common man. While this pandemic has forced several businesses to cut back or suspend operations, and unfortunately moving towards its bottom line, the advancement in technology-driven activities helped to accelerate all the event of many rising businesses. This is often very true for innovations that help back to establish human-to-human contact through distant ways, alter processes, and increase productivity amid social distancing. Due to which after COVID-19 pandemic, overall customer behavior also gets completely changed and encourages various new working patterns and norms. Customer can purchase additional merchandise and services on-line, technology made increase in the numbers of individuals who can easily work remotely. As economies slowly open up and companies move into the normal conditions, the use of Artificial Intelligence based computing (AI) will become more valuable in serving the world online with new trends and making it as a new normal.

Google Meet is a Google's video-conferencing platform, which surpassed fifty million downloads in the Play Store during COVID-19, As working from home is a new culture of working in various departments, which have fully grown to the top level during COVID-19. Due to this reason, Google Meet peak downloads by thirty times, during COVID-19. Google Meet is hosting three billion minutes of video conferences and adding roughly three million new users a day. Other similar platforms are also booming in the same industry, such as Zoom video conferencing platform, Cisco WebEx Meetings, GoToMeeting, Blue Jeans Meetings, join.me., Cisco Jabber, TeamViewer, Adobe Connect, etc.

Conclusions

COVID-19 has changed into a worldwide crisis, evolving at extraordinary pace and scale, Because of which no business is immune from its impact. Industrials and corporations facing grappling with the immediate impact of COVID-19 as each their producing and operations faced immediate incidents of such, and their customer's also face similar types of challenges in terms of having the reach towards their required level of products and services. It's crucial to see that

what will be the methods to make control over facing these challenges. Hence, the subsequent suggestions may be given, But we know that no 'one-size-fits-all' resolution to the problems facing Industrial because of the size and variety of the arena.

Industrial makers act currently to preserve the integrity of their operations and shield their individuals from making ready for ramping over their operations and therefore the post-COVID-19 situations may come under their controls. For such reasons several establishments choose a centre command system for speedy response deployment and quickly change operations associated continue to the response cycle. Businesses can't stop their production and workings for a very long period of time, for on-going performance capability establishment. All of this should be through with a selected focus and prioritization of their customers' core wants. The businessperson must have to fulfil the need for scaling up revenue goals and merchandise on timelines beside.

Small businesses ought to get on the look-out for borrower-friendly loans extended by government authorities. The depository financial institution of India had declared variety of measures that offered rupees 374,000 crores (US\$52 billion) to the country's economic system. Minister of finance, Nirmala Sitharaman has declared some details of the Atma-nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan package, to produce relief to Medium, Small, and small Enterprises (MSMEs) within the sort of a rise in credit guarantees. The government conjointly disclosed a low-cost loans program for farmers to shore up the agricultural economy. The perfect approach is to remain transparent together with your customers concerning what your business goes through. Maintaining a healthy relationship with creditors, investors, and contract parties will significantly helps in such situation of COVID-19 pandemic.

India is primarily an Agro-based country. In India, 70% rural population is relying upon agriculture. However, within the present era, because of urbanization, most rural residents migrated to urban areas like Pune, Mumbai, Delhi, Bengaluru, etc. for the employment and earning purposes. But because of COVID-19 pandemic all of such migrant workers get seriously affected and are actually not in the state of proper recovery on their own. And such migrant workers are somehow the backbone of the various manufacturing industries, as such will be required in the upcoming future also, for availing the work of labours and the workforces in various types of industries. That's why a proper support system mechanism is need of the hour in

such case, so that they will be able to stand again for contributing. Because they were badly suffering from the pandemic.

References

- [1] Al-Mansour, J., & Al-Ajmi, S. (2020). Coronavirus ‘COVID-19’ – Supply Chain Disruption and Implications for Strategy, Economy, and Management, *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(9).
- [2] Bacq, S., Geoghegan, W., Josefy, M., Stevenson, R., & Williams, T. A. (2020). The COVID-19 Virtual Idea Blitz: Marshaling social entrepreneurship to rapidly respond to urgent grand challenges. *Business Horizons*.
- [3] Cankurtaran, P., & Beverland, M. B. (2020). Using design thinking to respond to crises: B2B lessons from the 2020 COVID19 pandemic. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 88, 255–260.
- [4] Crick, J. M., & Crick, D. (2020). Coopetition and COVID-19: Collaborative business-to-business marketing strategies in a pandemic crisis. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 88, 206–213.
- [5] European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control data. Geographical distribution of 2019-nCoV cases. Available online: (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/geographicaldistribution-2019-ncov-cases>)
- [6] Imperial College London. Report 2: estimating the potential total number of novel coronavirus cases in Wuhan City, China. Jan. [disease-analysis/news--wuhan-coronavirus](https://www.imperial.ac.uk/news/2020/01/disease-analysis/news--wuhan-coronavirus), 2020.
- [7] Impacts on Work Productivity. (*The International Journal of Applied Business*), 4(1), 13–21.
- [8] Kuckertz, A., Brändle, L., Gaudig, A., Hinderer, S., Morales Reyes, C. A., Prochotta, A., Steinbrink, K. M., & Berger, E. S. C. (2020). Startups in times of crisis – A rapid response to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 13, e00169.
- [9] Lin, J., Li, L., Luo, X. (Robert), & Benitez, J. (2020). How do agribusinesses thrive through complexity? The pivotal role of e-commerce capability and business agility. *Decision Support Systems*, 113342.
- [10] Peiris, J. S. M., Lai S. T., Poon L. et. al. Coronavirus as a possible cause of severe acute respiratory syndrome. *The Lancet*, 2003; 361(9366): 1319- 1325
- [11] Ritter, T., & Pedersen, C. L. (2020). Analyzing the impact of the coronavirus crisis on business models. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 88, 214–224.

- [12] Reeves, M., Lang, N., & Carlsson-Szlezak, P. (2020). Lead Your Business Through the Coronavirus Crisis. In *Coronavirus and Business: The Insights You Need from Harvard Business Review*. Harvard Business Review.
- [13] Sharma, A., Rangarajan, D., & Paesbrugghe, B. (2020). Increasing resilience by creating an adaptive salesforce. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 88, 238–246.
- [14] Sheth, J. (2020). Business of business is more than business: Managing during the Covid crisis. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 88, 261–264.
- [15] Susser, P., & Tyson, T. (2020). What Are Companies’ Legal Obligations Around Coronavirus? In *Coronavirus and Business: The Insights You Need from Harvard Business Review*. Harvard Business Review.
- [16] Tarki, A., Levy, P., & Weiss, J. (2020). The Coronavirus Crisis Doesn’t Have to Lead to Layoffs. In *Coronavirus and Business: The Insights You Need from Harvard Business Review*. Harvard Business Review.
- [17] Tse, A. C. B., So, S., & Sin, L. (2006). Crisis management and recovery: how restaurants in Hong Kong responded to SARS. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 25(1), 3–11.
- [18] Wang, Y., Hong, A., Li, X., & Gao, J. (2020). Marketing innovations during a global crisis: A study of China firms’ response to COVID-19. *Journal of Business Research*, 116, 214–220.
- [19] WHO(2020). Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): Situation report (No. 94).
- [20] World Bank. (2020). World Bank Open Data | Data. GDP (Current US\$) | Data. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD>
- [21] Zenker, S., & Kock, F. (2020). The coronavirus pandemic – A critical discussion of a tourism research agenda. *Tourism Management*, 81, 104164.